

EVIDENCE OF CARBOXY ESTER MECHANISMS IN NITRIFICATION FROM THE DYNAMIC REACTION KINETICS AT NATURAL CONCENTRATIONS.

Part V. Single Carbon Analogues of Nitrification Substrates and Iron Bound Carbon Carboxy Esters.

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Abstract

The reaction kinetics of ammonia oxidation by nitrifying bacteria, following small ammonia pulses, conforms better to half order kinetics with a pseudo kinetic constant than Michaelis-Menten kinetics. This would indicate that hydroxamic acid, not hydroxylamine, is the true first intermediate in nitrification. Theorised mechanisms with carboxy esters allows for explanations to issues of toxicity, dynamic control and optimisation. In addition to oxidising ammonia, nitrifying bacteria can also oxidise C1 substrates, although they do not grow on them. This would suggest that C1 oxidation reactions by nitrifying bacteria use the same carboxy ester mechanisms and do not involve the simple transfer of electrons. ¹³C1 experiments with iron oxylate complexes indicate that nitric acid interferes with formaldehyde and formate hydrolysis. This suggests that C1 and N1 bacteria are probably inhibited by acids other than those used for the target substrate. The theorised carboxy ester N1 and C1 mechanisms would most likely predate the great oxidation event. They also suggest new N1 and C1 basic chemical routes.

Key words: Nitrification, C1 substrates, Mechanisms, Iron oxylate, Carboxy esters

1. Introduction

The theorised carboxy ester mechanisms described in previous papers [1] [2] can give an explanation to the process of nitrification, including the reaction kinetics, but there are carbon and sulphur utilizing bacteria with the corresponding substrate analogues. Indeed methane and methanol are often named as analogue substrates to ammonia and hydroxylamine respectively [3]. The question then arises as to what sort of substrates they are as *Nitrosomonas* do not grow on either. How do the alternative substrates react? Why is growth restricted? It may be argued that methanol is toxic and inhibits the reactions, whereby the same can be said of hydroxylamine, but how this happens has not been convincingly explained. Indeed "toxic inhibition" would have to be specific to the reactions to have merit as an explanation. How hydroxylamine inhibits ammonium mono-oxygenase at higher concentrations has not been established [4]. *Nitrosomonas europaea* is sensitive to single carbon molecules which has been described as mysterious [5] because they all have little complexing ability unlike their inhibitors. As the theorised carboxy ester route has carbamate as the reactant for ammonia mono-oxygenase, after the phosphate group is lost, this raises some important questions regarding the reactions of analogue substrates. The theorised reactions yield answers to observations made. The binding molecule (E) is assumed to use iron so that the resulting hydroxamic acid is stabilized. The carboxy ester route thus forms an iron complex. The subsequent hydrolysis reactions are theorised to involve nitrogen carboxy dimer chemistry.

Methanotrophs can oxidise ammonia [5] to nitrite and there are many similarities to nitrifiers. This paper examines how carboxy esters might explain the reactions involving single carbon molecules in both. In addition to the range of carboxy esters in the theorised nitrification mechanisms the involvement of a carboxy thiol ester could also be considered in a wider context.

1.1. Oxalic Acid Dimer Chemistry

Given that N1 substrates can be oxidised by C1 processing bacteria, this would suggest that both N1 and C1 biochemistry reactions involve carboxy

ester dimers. The theorised hydrolysis reactions were deemed to be C-N heterodimer paired based and that the carboxy group is bound to an iron atom. There is a C-C homodimer iron chemistry analogue in the adsorption of Fe^{III}-oxalate complexes on iron surfaces[6].

The Fe^{III}-oxalate complexes are formed with magnetite Fe₃O₄ and hematite Fe₂O₃. A pH-dependent equilibrium [7] is established between the two different surface > Fe^{III}-oxalate complexes. To make a mixture of carbon and nitrogen dimers adding nitrite to Fe^{III}-oxalate complexes can be considered as a starting point. The nitrogen analogue to oxalates are oxoacids which are known to make copper complexes.

Hydroxylamine in water, at high concentrations for biochemistry, binds with Fe^{III} and undergoes reactions to various nitrogen oxides [8]. Using hydroxylamine with Fe^{III}-oxalate complexes might thus thought to yield the nitrogen

oxides regardless of the presence of oxalic acid and thus it was seen as less instructive.

1.2. Oxidation of C1 Molecules with Hydrogen Peroxide

In aqueous iron hydroxide solutions formaldehyde, formate and methanol (as formaldehyde stabilizer) are oxidised in the presence of hydrogen peroxide [9]. It can thus be anticipated that ammonium monooxygenase would oxidise methanol. The building of the peroxide in turn requires electrons from the hydrolysis reactions. Thus for a successful utilization of single carbon molecules nitrifying bacteria would need to be able to generate electrons from a hydrolysis reaction. The carboxy ester hypothesis involves dimer pair reactions, in which one part is oxidised and the other reduced. If one of the molecules has a carbon atom, instead of the nitrogen atom, would the reaction proceed? Is this perhaps the reason why nitrifying bacteria do not grow on single carbon substrates?

Hydrogen peroxide is a common radical in water subjected to intense UV radiation, but UV radiation is also detrimental to proteins. It is then only with the energy from hydrolysis reactions that a controlled peroxide reaction can be achieved and especially in a dioxygen limited environment. Thus there is a more fundamental question, can Fe^{III} -oxalate complexes hydrolyse single carbon molecules without hydrogen peroxide? What is the influence of nitrogen oxide ions and phosphate ions on any dimer reactions?

2. Experimental

As oxalic acid is a dimer, it is possible that CO_2 could arise from its breakdown rather than any C1 oxidation reaction. To overcome this experimental issue ^{13}C 1 enriched C1 reactants were used with a corresponding blank. The methanol, formaldehyde and formic acid isotopes were ^{13}C 1 99% atom purity (Aldrich Chemistry, Germany). These were then diluted with their standard laboratory C1 equivalents so that the experimental results fell within the the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ instrument measurement range of the analysing laboratory (OEA laboratories, UK) equipment.

An iron hydroxide stock solution was made comprising of 5.4 g iron chloride hexahydrate and 2.8 g iron sulphate heptahydrate made up to 100 g of solution with deionised water. The oxalyic acid solution consisted of 1 g oxalic acid dihydrate 99% purity, 0.2 g iron powder of 99.5 % purity in 100 g deionised water.

For the experiments 150 ml beakers were filled with 10 g of the stock iron hydroxide solution and then diluted with 40 g of deionised water. A 2 wt % solution of sodium hydroxide was then added to achieve the various experimental pHs. The alkali solutions produced predominately magnetite. The C1 liquids (0.5 g methanol, 1.5 g formaldehyde and 0.5 g formate) were added to 12 g of the oxalic acid solution. For the nitrite (N) and nitrite/phosphate ion (NP) experiments 1 g of sodium nitrite 99 % purity and or 1 g of sodium pyrophosphate decahydrate 99 % purity were added to the oxalyic acid mixture.

Water was boiled in a stainless steel pressure vessel and the 4 beakers with the mixed iron hydroxide/oxalyic acid/C1 mixtures were placed in a basket above the water level. The pressure was quickly raised to 50 KPag and any air driven off. The conditions were then held for 30 minutes. Upon cooling CaOH of 95 % purity was used to trap any CO₂ as calcium carbonate. The solubility of calcium formate is considerably higher. The precipitate was filtered out with glass fibre paper and the dried filter paper sent for analysis. The analysing laboratory took duplicate samples from different areas of the filter paper and the results were consistent. It is thus assumed that variations, as seen in the blank determinations, are a result of the experimental conditions themselves.

3. Results

In table 1 formate is seen to be fully oxidised with the iron hydroxide/oxalic acid mixture under all pHs. The addition of nitric acid reduces the conversion by around half at lower pHs, which drops further at higher pHs. The nitric and phosphoric acid together lower the conversion still further. Formaldehyde oxidation follows similar trends to formate, with a lowered conversion. Although

Blank			$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ Increase		
pH	Acid	$\text{H}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$	CH_3OH	CH_2O	CH_2O_2
3		-29.0			67.4
3	N	-26.0	-4.4	35.4	48.7
3	NP	-33.2	3.4	22.4	34.8
5		-27.1	0.4	24.1	34.2
5	N	-26.0	-4.2	25.7	31.0
5	NP	-17.6	-13.6	19.1	15.8
7		-28.4	-2.2	18.8	60.8
7	N	-20.6	-10.3	9.4	34.8
7	NP	-18.9	-7.3	12.4	18.4
9		-33.4	9.5	25.7	56.6
9	N	-19.9	-11.2	13.1	23.6
9	NP	-22.7	-2.7	9.0	16.8
11		-25.2	4.2	9.2	61.6
11	N	-22.0	-0.5	7.7	7.0
11	NP	-19.6	2.8	13.3	-2.3

Table 1: Increase in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ from addition of ^{13}C 1 Reactants

phosphate ions bind to Fe^{III} hydroxides the hydrolysis reaction is not totally inhibited. The oxalic acid was in great excess and the experiments would suggest that Fe^{III} -oxalate complexes are formed with nitrite and phosphate replacing carboxylic acid. This in turn reduces the formaldehyde and formate conversion.

Under the conditions, in which dioxygen was excluded, methanol is not being significantly converted.

4. Discussion

The experiments have examined oxalic acid chemical reactions with analogues to carboxylic acid, outwith a biological setting. In combination with Fe^{III} -

oxalate complexes formaldehyde and formate are oxidised, presumably overall a hydrolysis reaction, to carbon dioxide. It is theorised that the reactions are akin to those envisaged for their theorised nitrogen analogues in biochemistry. The presence of nitrogen or phosphoric acids interferes with the reactions. Given that the nitrogen and phosphoric acid analogues are very similar in size and properties this is perhaps not surprising. It can thus be anticipated that the same inhibition will occur in a biological context. Thus a theorised iron stabilized dimer type reaction in nitrifying bacteria would undergo inhibition where single carbon analogues are present. This would reduce the desired hydrolysis reactions and in turn would reduce the number of electrons available for making a peroxide.

The experiments were conducted with oxalyic acid in great excess, but it can also be formed from two metal formate molecules. It then allows for catalysed reactions using pairs of the dimers whereby oxidation/reduction of them take place. The carboxy part binding to carbon, nitrogen, sulphur or phosphate molecules.

4.1. Industrial Chemistry and Redox Reaction Mechanisms

Nitrification and denitrification have been described in terms of redox reactions, involving the transfer of electrons, with the electrode potentials for the reactions being given. A redox mechanism for denitrification or Anammox reactions implies that enzymes complete redox reactions at much milder conditions than required in industrial chemistry.

Methanol oxidation using haematite Fe_2O_3 catalysts, whereby it is thought that magnetite Fe_3O_4 is the reactive form, have been shown to proceed via a methoxy mechanism [10].

At the absorption site X the species with the subscript a is absorbed:

The presence of (lattice) oxygen destabilizes the methoxy yielding formate. A monolayer of molybdena blocks the reaction so that formaldehyde is formed. The reaction step forming the methoxy can be seen to be a dimer reaction as has been theorised for the biochemistry mechanisms. The aqueous phase biochemistry mechanisms are carboxy ester based and would be deemed to occur at much milder conditions.

For copper based reactions it is theorised that oxoacids of nitrogen would be involved instead of oxalic acid. Nitrite and nitrate ions both build dimer complexes with copper. The hydrolysis reactions would then be achieved with the formation of a carbon nitrogen bond as in nitrification/denitrification.

4.2. Reaction Mechanisms and Evolution

The dimer reactions outlined for the nitrogen cycle, and the hypothesis that the C1 carbon biochemistry of nitrifiers is a variation of the same chemistry theme, raises wider issues regarding the evolution of the mechanisms. It is estimated that nitrifying bacteria are at least 2.5 billion years old [11], forming part of the nitrogen cycle involving dioxygen as an oxidant. Basic biochemistry mechanisms do not often change and thus the theorised hydrolysis mechanisms would be expected to be even older using other oxidants such as nitrates and sulphates. H_2S can also be oxidised by bacteria using nitrate rather than dioxygen and carboxy thiol esters might have been used as an energy source prior to ATP [12].

For evolution to operate it needs reactions that are self replicating, but which also give control and optimisation possibilities. Thus the role of iron/copper in combination with carboxy dimer ester pairs could play a part in explaining chemical reactions leading to life. The carboxy ester dimer chemistry, where iron and copper complexes bind to proteins, may lead to slightly lower entropy states. This in turn might give insights into the chiral nature of biochemical reactions.

In biochemistry the N1 and C1 reactions are taking place in an aqueous environment, rather than the gas phase with a solid catalyst used in industry, at low pressures and low temperatures. Proteins are made from complex carbon, nitrogen and sulphur molecules. Were the low temperature reactions to be only possible with complex proteins attached to the active site metal, then this raises questions on how they evolved. It has to be suspected that the reactions involving these atoms, the building stones of amines/proteins, occurred in evolutionary terms at the same time and that the reactions are a variations on a theme. Could the metals not have originally bound with other molecules, amino acids and then proteins thereby optimising the geometry of the dimer pair reactions? That chemical reactions occurred that could be optimised with proteins to yield lower energy states is surely much more probable than complex proteins to have developed that then incorporated metals to realise the reactions. The magnetic properties of magnetite, probably the reactive iron form, and that of UV light that influences C-N bonds and produces oxygen radicals are of note.

Work undertaken into microbial nitrogen-cycling [13] has determined the protein structures of enzymes, but the assumed substrates are simple ions that generate the required energy. Current mechanisms would have simple ion substrates producing mutagenic intermediates, but which then pass through the enzyme structures without any significant denaturing of them occurring.

Reaction kinetics gives insights into the mechanisms and in the case of ammonia oxidation at least, a two molecule multiple step reaction mechanism is supported. Are basic biochemistry reaction mechanisms not related to organic chemistry and in turn to carbon-metal chemistry? Ammonia and formic

acid could react to formamide and thus purine. Pyridine, that complexes with oxoacids, can be made from esters and formaldehyde.

4.3. A C1 and N1 Economy

C1 liquids such as methanol are basic industrial chemical building blocks. They are mostly derived from synthesis gas, a mixture of hydrogen and carbon monoxide, made from natural gas (methane). Hydrogen however is the lightest of gases and cannot be liquefied. Its storage requires very large pressures as the energy content depends upon the mass of hydrogen. Batteries store electrons, but use heavy metals whereby the lightest are rare. Energy density limits are also being reached due to safety considerations. Liquid fuels on the other hand are easily stored and transported, as well as having higher energy densities. The production of liquid fuels from renewable electricity on a local scale with subsequent storage is thus very attractive. In a reverse process liquid C1 fuels could then be used to produce electricity and heat.

The aqueous phase carboxy ester reaction mechanisms theorised would seem to offer such reaction possibilities as an alternative to the synthesis gas route. Carbon dioxide is dissolved in water and could be used in a concentrated form from the reverse reactions. The catalysts would employ iron and copper which are much more abundant than lithium for example. In biology the concentrations are very low, but in a man-made process this does not have to be the case nor need the temperature limits of proteins apply (higher efficiencies).

5. Conclusion

Nitric and phosphoric acids inhibit the oxidation of formaldehyde and formate by iron oxalate complexes in the absence of dioxygen. The way C1 molecules are processed by nitrifying bacteria can be understood if they form carbon bonds with carboxy dimer ester pairs. The molecules can be oxidised by an oxygenase, but are probably not hydrolysed to yield electrons which involve carbon nitrogen bonds. In a wider sense the reactions of ammonia, sulphur and

methane oxidising bacteria are theorised to be variations on a theme of carboxy ester dimer pair reactions.

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